

Nuclear Non-Proliferation Conundrum: Asymmetric Initiatives and Problem Areas of Nuclear Non-Proliferation Regime

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Abstract

Adeliberate effort has been made to identify the core causes and the consequent roots of nuclear proliferation, its related security concerns, and the international response to mitigate the nuclear technology's negative impact, leading to practical solutions. There is a need to forge a new consensus on the nonproliferation principles by the nuclear possessor states. This can happen through a dialogue between Nuclear Weapon States (NWS) and Non-NPT Nuclear Weapon States (Non-NPT NWS), i.e., India, Pakistan, and Israel. The study does not undermine the advantages of nuclear science, especially in the emerging challenges of the 21st Century, including the energy, water, and food shortages and complicated diseases in various parts of the world; it focuses on the discriminatory behavior of P-5 states towards the Non-NPT NWS. These challenges would continue to grow in new forms unless the major powers have a realistic evaluation of foreign policy objectives. It provides a detailed investigation of the international nuclear nonproliferation efforts, with the help of descriptive analysis to draw the claim that there is a dire need to take on board all the states having nuclear weapons in a legally bounding agreement to address the challenges of nuclear proliferation. Albeit, the social constructivist view holds that Non-NPT NWS along with NWS should be socialized into the positive-sum thinking of cooperative security under the umbrella of NPR. The article also elaborately covered the apprehensions to be addressed for enduring peace and international security.

Introduction

This year marks the 54th anniversary of NPT's entry into force, a significant moment of accomplishment; however, several challenges remain, and promises are left unfulfilled. The world still has over 13000 nuclear warheads, several under enhanced readiness, new sophisticated ballistic, cruise, and hypersonic weapons, alongside a drive toward autonomous weapons and integration of artificial Intelligence in nuclear force-related systems. To mitigate the envisaged risk regarding the proliferation of nuclear technology and usage of Weapons of Mass Destruction (WMD), despite several ongoing international, regional, and bilateral measures, the future of nonproliferation efforts seems unpredictable, uncertain, and unsatisfactory. While the U.S. and Russia have made reasonable progress toward nuclear nonproliferation efforts, including the safe disposal of spent fuel, however, Non-Nuclear Weapon States (NNWS) have severe reservations about the intent and the speed of moving toward general and complete Disarmament (Fact Sheet: Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty: 2017) as they have repeatedly been committing and recommitting during the NPT RevCons.

The research is focused on exploring a policy option to counter the future challenges of the Nuclear Proliferation Regime (NPR), and thus qualitative research method was applied. As "Qualitative research is a method of inquiry employed in many different academic disciplines, traditionally in the social sciences" (Kumar: 2011) therefore, the objective of the research is to gather detailed knowledge of the state's behavior concerning global institutions (Burn: 1994, 18-25). The study remained deductive research, which derives specific options to deal with the discussed problem. First, the research covers the existing data available on the subject area by conducting a detailed literature review. Then data analysis techniques are adopted to dig out the research findings.

The study applies systemic level analysis, as it highlights the dominant patterns of interaction among states, which ultimately helps deal with the system's problems more comprehensively. The study will also include the state-level analysis as an approach to understanding the role of the state in international politics (Burn: 1994, 18-25). The influential states, i.e., the US, Russia, etc., are analyzed as states having the capacity to influence other states. States are the primary determinants in world affairs, and their history, behavior, and attributes need to be analyzed deeply to recommend a policy that would be inclusive.

The literature available on the subject area is limited. Yet, the study has focused on reviewing the mechanisms of several nuclear nonproliferation initiatives through available fact sheets of those initiatives. The academic

resources are deducted through the process and objectives of the nuclear nonproliferation measures, even though these measures have always remained a sensitive issue for the states. Thus the existing records are not easily accessible chiefly due to the classified nature of the material. To cover this deficiency, secondary sources were explored that provide a comprehensive review of the treaties, cartels, and initiatives of NPR. Subsequently, the literature searched was narrowed down to only those initiatives directly bearing on this study. While conducting this research, there was a particular focus on the critical analysis of NPR and exploring a policy option to counter the future challenges.

After U.S. President's *atoms for peace* speech at the United Nations in 1953 eventually led to the establishment of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) to regulate nuclear energy sharing with numerous countries around the globe and to set up a comprehensive safeguard system that the recipient states do not utilize it for the attainment of military objectives (Weiss: 2003, 40). Sequel to the initiative of *Atoms for Peace* and the establishment of the IAEA triggered debate to setup a comprehensive Nuclear Non-Proliferation Regime (NPR) and culminated in the evolution of the NPT in 1968; it was conceived to streamline further the safeguard mechanism, which divided the countries into two categories: NWS and NNWS. NPT obligates the parties to waive nuclear weapons in alteration for the nuclear technology access for peaceful usage, including research and development under IAEA's well-regulated system. These efforts were intended to bring peace and stability globally and counter nuclear weapons proliferation. Yet, by not having the universal applicability, it was not attaining its prime goal of universalizing and filling the gaps of NPR.

Interestingly the whole debate on nonproliferation is intertwined with the constructivist notion. Therefore the study will provide the theoretical perspective of the nonproliferation regime by using the approved qualitative method. Consequently, to cover the gaps in the nonproliferation initiatives, it is essential to address nuclear have, not primarily the states which acquired nuclear weapons while remaining outside the framework of NPT. Therefore, managing them in the regime is imperative to enhance consistency and efficiency. Furthermore, these states should be allowed to modify the NPR as they now have nuclear weapons capability. Thus, taking them on board can improve the assistance, which is the spirit of these mechanisms.

Abolitionist Non-Proliferation Initiatives

There are various other nonproliferation initiatives under many different forums, such as the Conference on Disarmament (CD), Nuclear Security Summit (NSS), *Convention on Physical Protection of Nuclear Material* (CPPNM), Comprehensive Test Ban Treaty (CTBT), Fissile Material Cutoff Treaty (FMCT), *Negative Security Assurance [s]* (NSA), *Prohibition of Arms Race in Outer Space* (PAROS), *Global Threat Reduction Initiative* (GTRI) and many more. In addition, there are several other essential regimes/ arrangements, including the *Proliferation Security Initiative* (PSI), *Container Security Initiative* (CSI), *Mega Ports Initiative* (MPI), the *Global Initiative to Combat Nuclear Terrorism* (GICNT), and the initiative for creating *Global Partnership against the spread of WMD*, launched at the G-8 2002 Summit in the aftermath of 9/11. However, these are primarily the U.S. initiatives supported by like-minded countries to discourage non-state actors and other states aspiring to acquire sensitive nuclear technology using illegal means (Bassey: 2011, 92-132). Ironically, to address the issue of state's security motivations to acquire nuclear weapons, there is a need to reduce the salience of atomic weapons in the security doctrines of NWS (by limiting the role, reliance, and platforms), starting with the U.S., which should declare an NFU of nuclear weapons given its advanced conventional capabilities, along with other NWS.

Therefore, despite having some positive aspects, all these initiatives remained subject to criticism due to their ambiguous status in international law and difficulty checking their transparency. Subsequently, all these were partially successful steps to ensure the safety of sensitive materials and technology all around the globe (Gibbon: 2019). However, the only legal Treaty is Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty (NPT), although loopholes in the NPT do exist; therefore, the possibility of more proliferation of nuclear arsenals can't be ruled out in the coming days and years. Thus, the article draws an empirical claim that there is a need to introduce another treaty similar to NPT with more stringent measures than NPT to halt nuclear proliferation risks. Yet, it should board all the states with nuclear weapons technology, including India, Pakistan, Israel, and DPRK.

Because of its inherent weakness, the IAEA was not allowed to monitor the Democratic Republic of North Korea's (DPRK) complete nuclear activities during the late 1980s and 1990s. Similarly, it has failed to certify whether or not Iran was involved in the nuclear weapons development program. The ongoing trends and empirical evidence signify that unless the nuclear proliferation trends are identified in the initial stage, a remedial measure in the middle of the crisis is unlikely to be effective. As pointed out, Iran and DPRK are the two quotable examples. Therefore, while peaceful use of nuclear technology may be encouraged, effective safeguard measures must be placed before the foundation for extending peaceful nuclear technology.

The risk attached to the existing nuclear weapons and the vast stocks of Highly Enriched Uranium (HEU), separated plutonium, and unsafeguarded fuel remains a severe security concern globally. While the security challenges have further grown since 9/11, the states' global trends to generate nuclear energy as an alternate

option indicate that the possibilities of nuclear weapons technology proliferation will continue to grow unless an effective monitoring infrastructure, followed by stringent accountability, is enforced with immediate effect. For example, the published report of 2018 indicates that in January 2017, the HEU stockpiles were estimated to be 1340+125 tons globally. Similarly, in the same year, 520 tons of separated plutonium stockpiles were reported globally, among which 290 tonnes were in civilian custody.^{*}Therefore, capacity building of the IAEA, in addition to the signing of the IAEA-AP (Additional Protocol)[†](IAEA Safeguards Overview: 2020), would be a pre-requisite to effectively exercise control and achieve transparency of almost 449 Nuclear Power Plants (NPP), operating globally (Krikorian: 2020).

Nuclear Fuel Bank and IAEA

While taking parallel steps, the international community is also focusing on minimizing the opportunities of nuclear proliferation by giving the concept of *nuclear fuel bank*, managed collectively under an international arrangement. *President Eisenhower first broached the fuel bank idea in 1953, making little headway over the next two decades. A fuel bank would not be "a cure-all, but an added layer of oversight."*(Jorden: 2006). *It is estimated that substantial NPP would come up in the future to have an alternative means to generate energy. It would require heroic efforts to expand uranium mining and enrichment, and if they are centrally controlled, the possibility of nuclear proliferation would be reduced considerably.*

However, the consensus for an international uranium fuel bank is unlikely to be achieved easily. Most states would not like to give up the flexibility to have an independent status because of the changing nature of world politics and the trust deficits between the developed and developing states. This concept is against Article IV of the NPT, which authorizes the states to have a peaceful nuclear program in conformity with Articles I and II of the Treaty (Fact Sheet: Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty).

International concerns related to nuclear technology do not end here. The emerging trends in using atomic energy will likely introduce a new set of problems related to nuclear proliferation. The IAEA has been struggling and partially failed to address the issue of proliferation because of its limitations in terms of capacity and mandate. Mushrooming several NPP over the next two decades spread worldwide would be a gigantic task for the IAEA to manage, even if the countries involved have signed the IAEA-AP.

However, some scholars maintain that civilian nuclear technology sharing may increase the proliferation concerns, and scholars consider that the primary reason is the nuclear technology's dual-use nature (Fuhrmann: 2008, 633-652). Yet, the states should be granted permission to use peaceful nuclear technology as their sovereign right. Most significantly, unresolved disputes and security threats directly impact the states and their motivation to develop nuclear weapons capability, deteriorating the regional security environments. According to Fuhrmann, "peaceful aid increases the probability that countries will successfully build nuclear weapons" (Fuhrmann: 2008, 633-652), and mainly it is "true when a country's security environment deteriorates" (Fuhrmann: 2009, 8-9).

While the sad incident on March 12, 2011, at Fukushima (Japan Earthquake and Tsunami Update: 2011), Japan has forced the nuclear power possessor states to review their nuclear programs, there is no likelihood that the international community would give up the option of nuclear energy. Inadvertent risk of nuclear accidents notwithstanding, expansion of the NPP across the globe, including the states of the Gulf and Africa with the minor expertise, will add to the problems. Thus, greater cooperation and awareness at the national and international level would be an essential contributing factor to mitigating the nuclear proliferation risk and the possibility of nuclear technology/ material falling into the hands of non-state actors or terrorists. All the mentioned threats are equally applicable for the NWS and Non-NPT NWS, so both can join hands to counter these risks. In addition, a holistic approach to the ongoing problem, taking due cognizance of the states' security concerns, would usher the desired results nationally and internationally.

Organized Hypocrisy of P-5

The core international issues that may include national integrity, poverty, health, and education should be addressed on priority if one is sincere towards achieving stability within a country, in the region, and worldwide. A stable society would generate sufficient deterrence against a small percentage of extremist/ terrorist groups and non-state actors who are currently adamant about causing damage to the community by using any means, including access to the WMD. One must take away the oxygen from the terrorists by isolating them and taking away the motivation through which they can blackmail the public by exploiting the selected segment of society. P-5 should work in this direction as well instead of blocking the states access to peaceful transfer or sanctioning them.

^{*} Fissile Material Stockpiles, *International Panel on Fissile Materials*, Fostering Initiative to reduce stocks and end the production and use of highly enriched uranium and plutonium, <http://fissilematerials.org/>, accessed on February 2, 2022.

[†]IAEA-AP is a legal document which provides authority to the IAEA for further investigation/inspection in case of suspicious reports.

The 2018 U.S. Nuclear Posture Review states that Washington would deploy nuclear weapons to respond to non-nuclear strategic attacks. It also claims that the U.S. would develop low-yield nuclear weapons to keep the flexible response option open. This reemphasizes the growing salience of nuclear weapons for a state with the most advanced conventional militaries globally. This kind of review has far-reaching implications for Russian and Chinese nuclear doctrines. Moreover, it has a cascading effect on regional nuclear rivalries and promotes vertical proliferation. In the absence of a global norm to codify sheer proliferation, regional nuclear competition threatens global strategic stability. Developing usable (low-yield) nuclear weapons, hypersonic cruise missiles, and other emerging technologies that enhance nuclear readiness and counterforce targeting capabilities accelerate the arms race, undermine the prospects of arms control, and undermine nonproliferation.

Ironically, the great powers have remained the primary source of proliferation throughout history (Simpson: 1988, 34-50). The reason is the enormous stakes involved in the global nuclear black market, yet the developing states are blamed for the illegal involvement in the nuclear market. Many states exploited the current nuclear black market in the past. A.Q Khan was just one market link, as investigations indicated that its nodes were connected to UAE, Sudan, South Africa, Turkey, and Malaysia. Given the evidence shared by the U.S. with the government of Pakistan, A.Q Khan accepted his mistake and sought pardon from the public of Pakistan while appearing on national television. However, the ability of A.Q Khan to commit such a major blunder singlehandedly was also a matter of debate among analysts.

Nonetheless, several A.Q. Khans had been in over 40 countries, especially those possessing nuclear weapons. None of them could claim to have an indigenous nuclear program. In most cases, especially during the 1950s and 1960s, there had been a close collaboration between the front companies involved in nuclear technology proliferation and the government officials, including France, Israel, South Africa, etc. (Lieberman: 2001: 45-86).

Therefore, the international community must give up the blame game and take collective responsibility for all that has happened in the past. Taking the lead from the past, a wholesome approach involving the entire international community would be required to address the security issues related to nuclear proliferation. At the national and international levels, awareness would contribute to achieving the desired results. There is a need to introduce a new treaty with legal standing compared to all the conventions and arrangements highlighted in the preceding paragraphs. The introduced treaty can be part of a UN body like UNSC 1540. In letter and spirit, it should be taken seriously and implemented in all states (especially those with nuclear weapons technology).

Although the 21st Century has brought new challenges to global security, but at the same time, it has also provided opportunities to tackle this problem. An appraisal of the societal anxiety in various parts of the world would highlight that the root causes are not as much ideological or religious as they are a reaction to the discriminatory policies that tend to widen the north-south divide. Additionally, in underdeveloped regions, there is no food, no health care, no education, and no hopes for a better future. The leadership of these regions is struggling without any capacity to do so.

These regions are being exploited under one or the other pretext, including in the name of religion and ideology, thus, creating environments to drag other societies into a competition for domination and survival. Therefore, confidence between the nations must be restored by assuring the countries of disturbed regions that their national integrity will be respected. Settlement of the core issues by using force without carrots is likely to backfire and may generate more threats than peace and stability in the world. Therefore, the international community should realize that if they can address the root causes, they will be able to help the leadership of these regions cooperate more holistically without the fear of domestic fallout.

By signing the 123 Agreement,[‡] the US has already shaken the foundation of the NPT, which is at a crossroads. While the US is not expected to undo what it has done, it must ensure damage control. Failing to address current challenges related to the NPT could catalyze contagious acceleration of reliance on nuclear threats as national policies of the states, thus encouraging those not having this capability to acquire it. Resultantly, it will dramatically increase the risk of nuclear weapons use. On the other hand, an honest approach to implementing the regime parallel to the NPT regime in letter and spirit could offer the prospect of defeating all states' incentives to acquire nuclear arsenals. A peaceful resolution of the DPRK and Iran's atomic crises is critical to set the right course to help contain the potential NWS from initiating a new nuclear race, especially in the crises-prone regions.

Consequently, the NNWS could not restrain themselves from pursuing nuclear weapons-related programs because of their multiple security concerns. Accordingly, the emergence of NNWS as NWS has ensued in a significant hindrance to the universalizing of NPR. On the contrary, some scholars believe that "The United States projected its antinuclear ethos onto the world. But not everyone shared these values" (Bracken: 2012, 5).

[‡]123 Agreement is the US-India nuclear deal and NSG waiver given to India alone have become matters of concern for non-proliferation supporters, as this exceptional treatment will or likely to prove counter-productive for the non-proliferation norm.

Despite doing everything to foster antinuclear policies, the U.S. failed to universalize the NPT, as too much denial of nuclear reality and too much restraint resulted in chaos and flux. Hitherto, technically the non-NPT NWS cannot become part of the NPT as NWS, as the Treaty categorically mandated that only those states that had developed nuclear weapons before January 1, 1967, are the de facto NWS. Therefore, the international community must be aware of the causes of proliferation before attempting to bring stability due to the issue of nuclear proliferation in the Middle East, South Asia, and the Korean Peninsula. Unfortunately, the idea of persistent peace without nuclear weapons is more of a fiction than reality in this real world. Still, conditions can be created to address the underlying causes of proliferation to counter further horizontal proliferation. Interestingly there was no check on the vertical proliferation. Despite the signing of NPT in 1968, the NWS, particularly the US and the former Soviet Union Global, had piled up thousands of weapons. Therefore, efforts must ensure that all the non-NPT NWS remains associated with the NPR while dealing with the issues of their existing nuclear arsenals.

Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons (TPNW): Implication for the Proliferation Struggles

In the contemporary scenario with the military and technological advancement and modernization, the destructive capability of nuclear weapons presents a specific problem and threat to global security and safety. Moreover, the destruction capability of nuclear weapons is unendurable for humanity. To highlight the catastrophic implications of using nuclear weapons/explosive devices on humanitarian grounds, a non-government organization proposed a treaty formally called the TPNW, also known as the Nuclear Ban Treaty. The United Nations (UN) opened it up for signatures in 2017; the Treaty was ratified by 54 countries and entered into force in January 2021. While the five nuclear weapons states (NWS) under NPT and the other four did not sign this Treaty. After the ratification of the TPNW, the Secretary-General of the U.N. stated, "The culmination of a worldwide movement to draw attention to the catastrophic humanitarian consequences of any use of nuclear weapons. It denotes a meaningful commitment towards the complete elimination of nuclear weapons, which remains the highest disarmament priority of the United Nations" (U.N. Secretary-General's Spokesman: 2020).

This Treaty has a complete set of prohibitions on engaging or involving in some nuclear weapon campaign. According to the legal binding, the signatory states, after ratifying the Treaty, shall not be able to do not acquire nuclear weapons or any nuclear technology for the military objectives. Moreover, signatories are not allowed to conduct any test of nuclear explosive devices for military purposes. State parties of TPNWs don't produce any fissile material used for nukes. The initiative of the Treaty is to negotiate and legally bind the state parties to eliminate nuclear weapons. The effective negotiation of the Treaty enhanced the divergence among the international community, defenders, and antagonists in the effort to prohibit nuclear weapons. The defenders of the TPNW argue that this Treaty will fill the legal gap in the arms control and disarmament affairs under the NPT umbrella. Moreover, they argued that this initiative of the TPNW strengthened the NPT. This initiative will help prompt more crucial efforts to minimize the nuclear risk and promote nuclear disarmament.

While on the other hand, the opponents are against the TPNW. Nuclear weapons states under the NPT and other NWS and members of NATO have also baycoated the TPNW. Major powers like the US and UK also took part in the conference on *Humanitarian consequences of Nuclear weapons in Vienna*. While opposing the Treaty, they argued that this Treaty would detract the states from the previous treaties like the NPT and CTBT. This initiative talks about the complete Disarmament of nuclear weapons, while the states acquired such weapons to maintain stability and security in the hostile environment.

They argued that the elimination of nuclear weapons might affect the notion of deterrence because of instability and an increase in interstate conflicts. Some scholars argued that the challenging perspective from general nuclear nonproliferation to complete disarmament had raised various questions for world sovereign states. Due to nuclear deterrence, nuclear weapons have played a significant role in maintaining peace and stability around the world right after WW II and nuclear tests by the US. In addition, now the dynamics have been totally changed as the economic growth has risen compared to growth in WW-II, and the tolerance in society has decreased to a more civic society. Nuclear weapons are acting as peace stabilizers for smaller states.

The complete Disarmament of Nuclear Weapons has become a critical factor for the international community after TPNWs entered into force. The physical abolition will challenge the state's writ, the economic condition that is being protected by nuclear weapons along with borders; it will more likely put the world at the flank of breaking out of conventional wars. Moreover, the world's strategic stability will get disturbed as it will be challenging for countries to protect their allies and partners under a nuclear umbrella.

The pressing concern is that it will pressure the smaller states viz-a-viz conventionally strong countries. In short, for the security and stability of the state and regional stability, arbitration to terminate or eradicate the nukes and nuclear technology can be risky for the state. If conditions have no desire to take part in any chance in the process of nuclear abolishing, the objective of disarmament of nuclear weapons will never be attained. Therefore, to address the strategic stability and retain a peaceful environment in the region, there is a need to

highlight the risk associated with nuclear and provide the fundamental security for nukes. Thus, treaties like TPNW couldn't bring a solution, yet it is more important to work for modifying the NPR while taking on board all the nuclear weapons technology holder states.

Theoretical Prism of Constructivism and Non-Proliferation Regime

With the rising risk of terrorists/non-state actors, the states that commonly consider it problematic to collaborate even over routine issues have shown their readiness to support each other to counter the terrorist threat. Global struggles to counter nuclear terrorism must be assisted by unanimity and grounded on a similar approach. Besides, the P-5 or states with major stakes involved in the global industry of nuclear weapons proliferation ironically blame other developing countries for the trading and transportation of illegitimate nuclear technology. (Simpson: 1988, 10-35). In the past, the states exploited the prevailing black market of nuclear weapons (Simpson: 1988, 10-35). Yet, A.Q. Khan Network, which was not a solitary network, was being highlighted as it dealt with the developing states' proliferation. Moreover, the nodes of this network were inked to Malaysia, Sudan, United Arab Emirates (UAE), South Africa, and Turkey; most importantly, "the network also depended on a variety of unwitting manufacturing companies and suppliers on many continents" (Albright and Hinderstein: 2004). Additionally, to consider this incident as an offense of the state of Pakistan, despite the official statements given by Pakistan, which dwells upon the issue and proves that this episode was not government-sponsored. After the revelation, he was removed from leading KRL and put under house arrest with the charge taken from him so that he would not have access to all the nuclear-related technology (Musharraf: 2006, 50-96). Last year he died yet A.Q. Khan issue is still hindering Pakistan from acquiring peaceful nuclear technology. Nonetheless, Pakistan improved its nuclear safety and security mechanism, which is further developed and robust by some practitioners such as Cartwright, who commented that Pakistan's nuclear security system is one of the best systems in place (Cartwright: 2018). Yet, in consequence, Pakistan was penalized and denied peaceful technology. Moreover, while India's nuclear acquisition was connected to the nodes of the same proliferation network, India was granted an NSG waiver due to the bilateral interest of the US and India. The NPR initiatives depict the constructivist's approach in which reality is portrayed in a way that: "The meanings in terms of which action is organized arise out of 'interaction' and great powers exploit these regimes for their national interests and then "identities (or interests) are produced in and through 'situated activity,'" (Wendt: 1992, 391-425) which established the whole mechanism of NPR. The objectives of these mechanisms are meant to bring global stability and peace, but they secure the interests of the great powers implicitly. We may contend that NPR initiatives were shaped so that they oblige the powerful states' securities/national interests and use these regimes as a pressure tactic for the developing states. Krasner argues that "if the principles, norms, rules, and decision-making procedures become less coherent, or if the actual practice is increasingly inconsistent with principles, norms, rules, and procedures, then a regime has weakened" (Krasner: 1982, 186). This can be addressed by cooperation on equal footing and thus can result in a constructive outcome.

Robert Jervis also explained fear and its importance in constructing state behavior. Once aroused as a purpose of improbability about others' intents, anxiety can secure the existence of its own with a tendency to become a powerful driver of the security dilemma and spiral (Jervis: 1976). Moreover, fear is strengthened by other subjective factors (for example, nationalism), forcing a state to concede another state's peacemaking gestures by adopting hawkish rhetoric. Interestingly theoretical approach is needed that can successfully combine a focus on an objective understanding of state behavior and decision making while also explaining the psychological and cognitive processes that guide subjective phenomena like intentions, perceptions, and attribution. Albeit, the social constructivist view holds that Non-NPT NWS and NWS should join hands to modify the whole system of NPR.

Conclusion

Although the most frequently referred to as a success story, the NPT remained inconclusive for four decades after it entered into force (EIF) in 1970. The P-5 countries have not honored their commitment to general and complete disarmament as enshrined in Article VI of the Treaty. Therefore, the issue of nuclear disarmament is under discussion in the CD, along with other core subjects, including the FMCT, Negative Security Assurance (NSA), and PAROS. Still, on priority, except for the FMCT, all other issues have gone down to the bottom of the CD plan because of the vested interest of the P-5. Consequently, the CD remains in a logjam for several years that continues to cause frustration among the member states (Pomper and Crail: 2009). Furthermore, the unpredictability of the global security landscape suggests that the NPT's principle of NWS and NNWS would come under tremendous pressure in the future. It will erode the credibility of the NPT as it will become challenging to balance the three fundamental principles of the NPT (Fact Sheet: Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty).

Preceding in perspective, it is imperative to assess the causes of nuclear proliferation, particularly in South Asia, the Middle East, and the Korean Peninsula, and address the weaknesses of existing nonproliferation and arms control regimes. It is observed that while remaining aware of individual states' specific security and threat

perceptions, Non-NPT NWS can be brought under the nuclear arms control regime by addressing their security concerns similar to P-5 security concerns.

Threats related to the nuclear arsenals held by the NWS beside, today, the world community is also confronted with other kinds of threats emanating from terrorist groups using the concept of 4th generation warfare (4GW) or irregular warfare, employing conventional munitions to the use of WMD, while working outside states' control. Moreover, the future trends in nuclear technology's peaceful use to diversify the resources to have sustainable energy security could bring renewed concerns regarding the safety and management of NPP and the safe disposal of spent fuel. Given the cost increase in fossil fuel and natural gas and rising concerns about climatic change, many in the nuclear industries hope for a three to four-fold increase in global nuclear capacity by 2050.

In the light of emerging technologies in the 21st Century (i.e., Cyber, Space, A.I., C3I), the world had changed since 1968, when NPT entered into force (EIF). Accordingly, the international community needs to modify the mechanisms of the regimes to address new venues of policy making to address the nuclear proliferation concerns comprehensively. Thus there is a need to take concrete measures to address that apprehension. The continued nuclear modernization programs within the US and Russia that account for over 90 percent of the world's nuclear arsenal and other NWS is a challenge to the NPT Article VI commitments. Nonetheless, the ongoing global security problems can't be dealt with with a conservative approach alone. At the worldwide level, NPT needs to be strengthened by taking on board the Non-NPT NWS and NWS to curtail the emerging security threats, particularly nuclear terrorism and other impending concerns. Lastly, if the global vis-a-viz regional powers remain anarchic, then the great powers will continue dominating the world regimes. The significant task is to reinvent or replace the NPT and take on board all the nuclear weapons technology holder states under the proposed regime to overcome future security threats. *However, achieving this goal in the foreseeable future is impossible; nevertheless, a beginning must be made.*

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